

Cation Exchange Studies of Copper (II) Nitroso-R-Salt Complexes

ASHOK MAHAN & ARUN K. DEY*

Chemical Laboratories, University of Allahabad, Allahabad

Received 17 February 1972

Equilibrium distribution measurements of copper (II) at three constant ionic strengths (0.1, 0.5, 1.0 M, NaNO₃) as a function of nitroso-R-salt (NRS) with a number of cation exchangers have been studied and compared with the distribution of free metal ions. The monocomplex of copper does not exchange in the case of Dowex 50W-X12, while exchange occurs with Dowex 50W-X8 and -X4. Stepwise formation constants of the complex species in aqueous phase were computed to be $\log K_1^{\mu=0}$ and $\log K_2^{\mu=0}$ as 8.63 and 5.70 respectively at 30°.

Sodium-1-nitroso-2-naphthol-3,6-disulphonate (nitroso-R-salt, NRS) forms coloured complexes with various metal ions. Dey *et al.*¹ studied the stepwise equilibria in copper(II)-NRS system using spectrophotometric measurements. The same system has now been studied by cation exchange technique and the step formation constants have been determined by the procedures of Fronaeus² and of Loman-van Dalen³.

EXPERIMENTAL

AnalaR cupric nitrate was dissolved in water acidulated with nitric acid ($pH = 3.5$) and was standardized against EDTA. NRS (B.D.H.) solution was prepared by dissolving an exactly weighed amount in dilute nitric acid (pH as above).

All other chemicals used were of reagent grade.

The cation exchangers, Dowex 50W-X12, -X8, and -X4 (designated as (A), (B), and (C) respectively in this paper) were pretreated with EDTA solution ($\approx 0.02M$, $pH = 9 \pm 1$), followed by washing with water and then with acid (HCl). Thereafter they were treated with sodium chloride solution till the effluent became neutral to litmus and finally washed with water till free from chloride. After suitable drying by suction on a sintered glass filter, the air-dried resins (sodium form) were stored.

Procedure : pH -Measurements were done with a L & N pH -indicator using glass-calomel electrode assembly. For absorbance measurements a Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer using 10 mm matched glass cuvettes was employed.

The batch equilibration method was employed for distribution studies. Weighed amounts of the air-dried resin were added to the cupric nitrate solution ($2 \times 10^{-4} M$) containing varying amounts of NRS, maintained at $pH = 3.5$ and constant ionic strengths of 0.1, 0.5 and 1.0 M (NaNO₃) respectively. After shaking mechanically for two hours, the resin

* To whom all correspondence should be addressed.

was filtered off and the complex in the filtrate decomposed by bromine. The metal ion concentration in the solution was determined spectrophotometrically using 4-(2-thiazolyazo) resorcinol (TAR)⁴. A large number of experiments were performed and typical data were treated for the calculations.

The uptake of metal by the exchanger was calculated from⁵

$$\bar{R} = [v_0(R' - R\delta)]/g \quad \dots (1)$$

\bar{R} , R' , and R being the amounts of the metal in μg per gram of resin, per ml of original, and per ml of solution after equilibration with the exchanger; v_0 the added volume of the original solution in ml and g the amount of resin in gram. The values of the swelling factor (δ) of the resin were taken from literature⁶.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The distribution quotient, Λ , of copper between the exchanger and the solution as a function of the ligand concentration $[\text{NRS}]$, is related to the stability constants, β_n , of the complexes by^{2,7}

$$\Lambda = \lambda_0 \frac{1 + \sum_{n=1}^{n-1} \lambda'_n [\text{NRS}]^n}{1 + \sum_1^n \beta_n [\text{NRS}]^n} \quad \dots (2)$$

Fig. 1. Plot of λ_0/Λ vs $[\text{NRS}]$

(a) $\mu = 0.1$; (b) $\mu = 0.5$, and (c) $\mu = 1.0$.

where λ_0 is the distribution coefficient of metal ion in absence of the ligand, and the quantity λ'_n , which is related to λ_n (distribution coefficient of the n th complex), is given as

$$\lambda'_n = \lambda_n \beta_n / \lambda_0 \quad \dots (3)$$

The concentration of available NRS anion for complexation was calculated from the proton-ligand (HNRS) stability constant, K , by the relation⁸

$$\log [\text{NRS}] = \log [\text{HNRS}]_{\text{tot}} - \log(1 + K(\text{H}^+)) \quad \dots (4)$$

The literature values⁹ of K in the above are 6.95, 6.80, and 6.70 at $\mu = 0.1, 0.5$, and 1.0 respectively.

The first columns of Tables 1, 2 and 4 represent the concentrations of the anion of NRS after calculating from total NRS taken with the help of above equation. The values of λ_0 for different resins and at different ionic strengths are given in Table 1 in first horizontal rows. The plots of the experimental data λ_0/Λ against $[\text{NRS}]$ were obtained for each resin and at every ionic strength, then the values of λ_0/Λ (Table 1) corresponding to varying appropriate concentrations of NRS were read from the curves (Figure 1a, b and c).

The Fronaesus' procedure requires the graphical extrapolation of the function F'_1 and F'_2 (successively derived from F'_1) to zero NRS concentrations. Since all functions are almost linear, hence the errors of the derived functions must be within limits and the accumulative error in the final results is not excessively large as seen from the results. The linear plots of F'_1 vs F'_2 were obtained, this indicates that only 1:2 (Cu : NRS) species is the final complex formed under experimental conditions, therefore, β_1 and β_2 were directly determined as slope and intercept respectively from these straight lines. The calculated values of the functions F'_1 and F'_2 are summarized in Table 2.

In Loman-van Dalen treatment, the quantities λ'_1 (Table 3) were evaluated from the linear plots of the intermediate functions and the function F has been determined from these. Then the final functions F_1 and F_2 have been evaluated from F (Table 4) and the stability constants as their limiting values when plotted against $[\text{NRS}]$. The curves from which the values of λ'_1 have been evaluated are linear. In case of resins (B)–(C) the points of the plot are not much closer, though the nature of the curve is a straight line giving the value of λ'_1 as slope and intercept for resins (B) and (C) respectively. For resins (A)–(B) and (A)–(C) linear curves are obtained parallel to axis giving the $\lambda'_1 = 0$ in case of resin (A), while for resins (B) and (C) the values are in agreement with those of obtained in case of resins (B)–(C).

The values of the constants obtained with different resins are summarized in Table 5. The values of the step constants were extrapolated to zero ionic strength from plots of $\log K_n$ vs μ .

The colour reactions of NRS were affected by perchlorate, and hence sodium nitrate was used for maintaining ionic strength. Under the experimental conditions NRS was not sorbed by the resins, and therefore, the equilibrium concentrations of NRS could directly be obtained from equation (4). The electrolyte sorption for NRS was also negligible and has been ignored.

TABLE 1

Values of λ_0/Λ (read from Curves)

(a) $\mu = 0.1$			
[NRS] $M \times 10^6$	A	B	C
0.00	1442	591	436
0.90	230	160	134
1.00	260	175	145
1.10	292	192	158
1.20	325	210	169
1.30	363	227	180
1.40	400	245	190
1.50	440	262	201
1.60	480	277	213
1.70	525	295	225
1.80	570	312	236
1.90	617	328	249
2.00	667	345	262
2.10	720	366	276
2.20	780	390	292
2.30	845	415	308
2.40	923	443	325

(b) $\mu = 0.5$			
[NRS] $M \times 10^6$	A	B	C
0.00	156.00	68.50	44.30
1.25	30.00	22.00	16.00
1.50	37.00	25.50	18.00
1.75	44.00	28.50	20.00
2.00	51.50	32.50	22.00
2.25	60.00	35.00	23.50
2.50	68.00	38.00	25.00
2.75	77.00	41.50	26.50
3.00	86.00	45.00	28.00
3.25	97.00	48.50	30.00
3.50	115.00	52.00	32.50

(c) $\mu = 1.0$			
[NRS] $M \times 10^6$	A	B	C
0.00	6.00	3.40	2.90
1.75	2.05	1.53	1.42
2.00	2.20	1.60	1.47
2.25	2.37	1.68	1.51
2.50	2.53	1.75	1.55
2.75	2.72	1.83	1.60
3.00	2.90	1.90	1.64
3.25	3.08	1.97	1.69
3.50	3.28	2.03	1.73
3.75	3.45	2.08	1.78
4.00	3.65	2.14	1.82
4.25	3.86	2.18	1.86
4.50	4.10	2.21	1.91

TABLE 2

Treatment of the Data by the Method of Fronaeus(a) $\mu = 0.1$

[NRS] $M \times 10^6$	$F'_1(A)$ $\times 10^{-6}$	$F'_1(C)$ $\times 10^{-6}$	$F'_2(A)$ $\times 10^{-16}$	$F'_2(C)$ $\times 10^{-16}$
0.90	254.44	147.77	5.46	2.72
1.00	259.00	144.00	5.56	2.65
1.10	264.54	142.72	5.68	2.63
1.20	270.00	140.00	5.80	2.58
1.30	278.46	137.69	5.98	2.54
1.40	285.00	135.00	6.12	2.49
1.50	292.66	133.33	6.29	2.46
1.60	299.37	132.50	6.43	2.46
1.70	308.23	131.76	6.62	2.43
1.80	316.11	130.55	6.79	2.40
1.90	324.21	130.52	6.96	2.40
2.00	333.00	130.50	7.15	2.40
2.10	342.38	...	7.35	...
2.20	354.09	...	7.61	...
2.30	366.95	...	7.88	...
2.40	384.16	...	8.25	...

(b) $\mu = 0.5$

[NRS] $M \times 10^6$	$F'_1(A)$ $\times 10^{-6}$	$F'_1(B)$ $\times 10^{-6}$	$F'_1(C)$ $\times 10^{-6}$	$F'_2(A)$ $\times 10^{-14}$	$F'_2(B)$ $\times 10^{-14}$	$F'_2(C)$ $\times 10^{-14}$
1.25	23.20	16.80	12.00	4.54	3.28	2.34
1.50	24.00	16.33	11.33	4.70	3.19	2.20
1.75	24.57	15.71	10.86	4.81	3.07	2.11
2.00	25.25	15.50	10.50	4.90	3.03	2.04
2.25	26.22	15.11	10.00	5.14	2.95	1.94
2.50	26.80	14.80	9.60	5.25	2.89	1.86
2.75	27.64	14.73	9.27	5.41	2.87	1.80
3.00	28.33	14.66	9.00	5.55	2.86	1.74
3.25	29.54	14.61	8.92	5.79	2.85	1.73
3.50	32.57	14.57	9.00	6.38	2.84	1.74

(c) $\mu = 1.0$

[NRS] $M \times 10^6$	$F'_1(A)$ $\times 10^{-4}$	$F'_1(C)$ $\times 10^{-4}$	$F'_2(A)$ $\times 10^{-11}$	$F'_2(C)$ $\times 10^{-10}$
1.75	60.00	24.00	2.90	9.41
2.00	60.00	23.50	2.94	9.20
2.25	60.88	22.66	2.98	9.05
2.50	61.20	22.00	3.02	8.87
2.75	62.54	21.81	3.07	8.65
3.00	63.33	21.33	3.11	8.47
3.25	64.00	21.23	3.15	8.29
3.50	65.14	20.85	3.20	8.13
3.75	65.33	20.80	3.23	7.98
4.00	66.25	20.50	3.28	7.84
4.25	67.29	20.23	3.32	7.71
4.50	68.88	20.22	3.39	7.60

TABLE 3

Values of Quantities λ'_1

\bar{n}	$\lambda'_1(A)$		$\lambda'_1(B) \times 10^{-5}$		$\lambda'_1(C) \times 10^{-5}$	
0.1	0.00	0.00	4.60	4.66	7.80	7.79
0.5	0.00	0.00	3.10	3.10	6.95	6.86
1.0	0.00	0.00	1.80	2.00	2.55	2.75

TABLE 4

Values of Functions F , F_1 and F_2 (a) $\mu = 0.1$

[NRS] $M \times 10^6$	$F(B)$	$F(C)$	Average F^* (A,B,C)	$F_1 \times 10^{-8}$	$F_2 \times 10^{-13}$
0.90	226.24	228.07	228.10	2.52	7.48
1.00	255.50	258.10	257.87	2.57	7.19
1.10	289.15	293.56	291.57	2.64	7.20
1.20	325.92	327.18	326.03	2.71	7.15
1.30	362.74	362.52	362.75	2.78	7.17
1.40	402.78	397.48	400.08	2.85	7.15
1.50	442.78	436.17	439.65	2.92	7.16
1.60	480.87	478.82	479.90	2.99	7.15
1.70	525.69	523.35	524.68	3.08	7.24
1.80	570.34	567.34	569.23	3.16	7.26
1.90	614.67	618.02	616.56	3.24	7.32
2.00	662.40	670.72	666.71	3.33	7.39
2.10	719.55	728.09	722.55	3.44	7.64
2.20	784.68	793.07	785.92	3.57	7.81
2.30	854.07	860.55	853.20	3.70	8.01
2.40	932.07	933.40	929.49	3.87	8.43

(b) $\mu = 0.5$

[NRS] $M \times 10^6$	$F(B)$	$F(C)$	Average F^* (A,B,C)	$F_1 \times 10^{-6}$	$F_2 \times 10^{-12}$
1.25	30.52	30.00	30.14	23.31	2.89
1.50	37.36	36.90	37.09	24.06	3.04
1.75	43.96	44.50	44.15	24.66	2.83
2.00	51.84	52.80	55.05	25.52	2.91
2.25	59.41	60.51	59.97	26.21	2.89
2.50	67.45	68.75	68.07	26.83	2.85
2.75	76.88	77.51	77.23	28.08	3.04
3.00	86.85	86.80	86.55	28.52	2.94
3.25	97.36	98.25	97.54	30.01	3.17
3.50	108.42	112.12	111.84	31.95	4.07

(c) $\mu = 1.0$

[NRS] $M \times 10^6$	$F(B)$	$F(C)$	Average F^* (A,B,C)	$F_1 \times 10^{-5}$	$F_2 \times 10^{-10}$
1.75	2.01	2.05	2.04	5.94	3.10
2.00	2.18	2.22	2.20	6.00	3.00
2.25	2.36	2.38	2.37	6.09	3.06
2.50	2.54	2.54	2.54	6.16	3.04
2.75	2.74	2.72	2.72	6.25	3.10
3.00	2.93	2.89	2.90	6.33	3.11
3.25	3.12	3.09	3.10	6.46	3.26
3.50	3.31	3.27	3.29	6.54	3.26
3.75	3.48	3.48	3.47	6.58	3.16
4.00	3.68	3.68	6.67	6.67	3.19
4.25	3.85	3.87	3.86	6.73	3.13
4.50	4.00	4.10	4.07	6.82	3.16

* Values of $F(A)$ as in Table 1 have been considered in obtaining the average.

TABLE 5

Values of Stability Constants at Different μ

	$\mu = 1.0$		$\mu = 0.5$		$\mu = 0.1$		$\mu \rightarrow 0$	
	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$
<i>Fronaeus' method :</i>								
Resin (A)	5.72	4.54	7.30	5.70	8.33	5.57	8.70	5.75
Resin (B)	7.28	5.44
Resin (C)	5.70	4.66	7.30	5.48	8.27	5.38	8.65	5.65
<i>Loman-van Dalen method</i>	5.73	4.77	7.29	5.18	8.34	5.54	8.65	5.70
<i>Average values</i>	5.72	4.65	7.29	5.45	8.31	5.50	8.63	5.70

In each system no sorption of the cationic species was observed with resin (A); thus the value of F was determined directly as

$$F = 1 + \sum_1^n \beta_n [\text{NRS}]^n = \lambda_0 / \Lambda$$

The values of λ_0 / Λ , as given in Table 1 for resin (A) are omitted from Table 4, but are considered in obtaining the average values of F . No explanation is possible under present investigations for almost equal values of K_2 at lower ionic strengths. The average values of logarithms of $K_1^{\mu=0}$ and $K_2^{\mu=0}$ are 8.63 and 5.70 respectively.

The authors thank the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, for support.

R E F E R E N C E S

1. T. Singh, A. Mahan and A. K. Dey, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.* 1972, **34**, 2551.
2. S. Fronaeus, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1951, **5**, 859; *Svensk Kem. Tidskr.*, 1953, **65**, 19
3. H. Loman and E. van Dalen, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 2037.
4. M. Hnilicková and L. Sommer, *Talanta*, 1966, **13**, 667.
5. A. J. Zielen, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 5022.
6. A. Mahan and A. K. Dey, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem* (in press).
7. B. G. F. Carleson and H. Irving, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 4390.
8. A. Mahan and A. K. Dey, *Anal. Chim. Acta* (in press).
9. S. Mandal and A. K. Dey, *Rev. Chim. Minérale*, 1968, **5**, 773.